

A study on the progress of the not succeed in the communication about the Career Guidance on the enrolment and labour marketing in the Thailand

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined to disconnect between career guidance, undergraduate study choices at universities, and Thailand's labor market requirements. The primary assumptions and practices that influence graduates of Kanchanaburi Rajabhat University's readiness to meet Thai labor market priorities are the subject of this study. In order to make this alignment easier, the research paper proposes marketing communications principles.

While Thailand continues to raise educational standards, approximately one million university graduates remain unemployed. The contribution of university graduates' human capital is approximately 7-10 percent of Thai GDP. According to the findings of the research, there is a disconnect between the demand for graduates and the supply of graduates due to a lack of interaction between education and industry. In order to bridge the gap between university graduates' unemployment and the requirements of the Thai labor market, the purpose of this research paper is to investigate career guidance for university students.

The findings of the study point to a number of pertinent issues, such as a disjointed and uncoordinated approach to career counseling for Thai students, which leads to a mismatch between the number of people enrolling in university courses and the reality of the job market. Additionally, despite the fact that representatives of the government and employers have long expressed concerns regarding graduate career uptake, there is a dearth of coordinated career counseling marketing communications.

According to the findings, students entering Thai universities are unaware of the priorities of the Thai labor market and the career opportunities associated with them. Additionally, the research demonstrates that curricula at Thai universities are typically not appropriately attuned to the requirements of the labor market. However, mitigating factors are mentioned to suggest reasons for this that Thai universities cannot address.

Based on seven key aspects that emerge from the research results, it is concluded that the Thai government may reconsider its investment in career guidance marketing communications: identity and ownership; a unified voice; customer centeredness; spelled out goals and objectives; budget and assessment; collaboration and complexity; a focus on solutions; and make a well-informed decision.

Key Words: career guidance, unified voice, marketing communications, counseling.

INTRODUCTION

This research paper examines career guidance, undergraduate degree selection, and Thailand's labor market requirements. It is based on two contradictory pieces of data. First, approximately one million university graduates in Thailand remain unemployed (Bangkok Post, 2011); second, there is a significant shortage of university graduates in Thailand who are skilled in entrepreneurship, general thinking, innovation, math, science, English, and information technology (World Bank, 2012a). In order to bridge the gap between graduates' unemployment and the requirements of the Thai labor market, this research paper investigates the career guidance of university students. The research is carried out at the Kanchanaburi Rajabhat University setting. According to the findings of the study, there is a disjointed career guidance service in Thailand with few relevant marketing communications to inform students about how to better align undergraduate degree choices with the needs of the labor market.

The dominant assumptions and practices that influence graduates of Kanchanaburi Rajabhat University's readiness to fulfill Thailand's priorities for the labor market are examined in this research paper, as are the marketing communications principles that facilitate this alignment. Thailand's higher education enrollment increased by 6.7% between 2001 and 2006, which is not in line with employment projections. Chalamwong et al. (2012) do not consider the increase in graduates to be sustainable because, by 2020, industry demand for graduates will plateau if universities continue to produce theoretical graduates at odds with employer demands for applied skills. Despite the fact that higher levels of education in Thailand contribute to higher total lifetime income (Pattamasiriwat et al. 2012),

According to World Bank (2008) and Chalamwong et al. (2012), graduates in Thailand lack computer skills, creativity, problem-solving abilities, tenacity, and discipline. According to Chalamwong et al. (2012), Thai employers place a higher value on these qualities than universities do on a high grade point average. Thailand's chances of joining the AEC in 2015 are not helped by this.

While graduates believe that higher education is essential for acquiring the skills necessary for employment, few Thai graduates believe that higher education provides the skills they require. According to Yilmaz's (2010) research, it takes export and foreign direct investment companies five to seven weeks to fill professional positions. Twenty-two percent of export and foreign direct investment companies say that graduate applicants lack technical skills, and 18 percent say that university applicants lack basic skills.

The inadequacy of Thai university undergraduate education outcomes with Thai labor market requirements and the significance of career guidance are the foundations upon which this research paper is based. The relationship between career guidance, university enrollment, and the Thai labor market is influenced by a number of interconnected factors that were mentioned earlier. The significance of the research topic is established by these elements. One of the eight major themes is the extensive literature on career guidance and its connection to university enrollment and the Thai labor market.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

The findings of this research paper support the recommendations made at the UNESCO Bangkok meeting in 2006 to address graduate unemployment. These recommendations were not implemented, so graduate unemployment persists.

Specifically:

- There is a dearth of information regarding the Thai labor market's supply and demand;
- Web-based portals and bulletin boards that are easy to use are needed as a way to communicate and gather information about the labor market and education;
- There is a dearth of accurate career information and advice;
- Government agencies, businesses, and educational institutions do not take career guidance in a coordinated manner;
- Information regarding digital media career guidance is lacking.
- The educational significance of the 11th National Economic and Social Development Plan is confirmed by this study's findings. Specifically: Thailand's development is still hampered by the poor quality of education reform; It is essential to place an emphasis on human capital development.
- Employers, the unemployed, and government ministries do not work together well;
- Parents and students lack awareness of the significance of career counseling;
- To help undergraduate students realize the significance of career guidance, government ministries must implement an integrated strategy;
- Youth need to be provided with comprehensive information about emerging skills needed for work and entrepreneurship;
- Regarding the Thai labor market, it is necessary to establish information links quickly between the public and private sectors.

However, contrary to what is suggested in Section 2.5 above, the findings of this research paper do not support the expectation that Thai students will follow their parents' instructions regarding university study and career choice. This research paper's findings come to the opposite conclusion: The choice of what to study at university appears to be largely up to the student, and parents appear to agree.

FURTHER, FINDINGS OF THIS RESEARCH PAPER INCLUDE:

The Thai Ministries of Education and Workforce need to:

- Use a brand identity that defines the requirements that career guidance fulfills for students, parents, and the national economy to raise awareness of career guidance;
- Use a service-oriented logic to encourage educators, students, parents, and employers to work with the government to continually improve career guidance, marketing, and service communications;

The Thai government must create a single authority with ownership of and responsibility for career guidance: that is, a single ministry or coordinating body to provide a collaborative model that satisfies a higher level of interest than the separate authorities' current operations;

- To raise awareness of career guidance and potential labor market absorptive capacity, the single authority must employ a marketing communications strategy;
- The sole authority needs to select a specific positioning statement for the career guidance brand that conveys the brand's values to students and parents and is consistent across all media channels;
- In order to help students make more educated career choices that are in line with the priorities of the Thai labor market, career guidance in Thailand needs to be reoriented away from being focused on bureaucracy and toward being focused on students. This could be accomplished by providing students with incentives to access government data.

The aim and objectives of career guidance delivery must be informed by student and industry career guidance, and they must be evaluated annually to inform career guidance service provision and marketing communications.

In order to determine the value of career guidance delivery and staff in order to make decisions, take actions, and deliver continuous improvement of the guidance service, including directions for necessary changes and a measure of the return on investment, a career guidance budget needs to be defined and evaluated.

In order to provide a suite of interconnected services that meet quality standards, it is necessary to synergize the complexity of the current multiple approaches to career guidance in Thailand.

The Thai government must clarify the supply and demand-driven nature of higher education in order to absorb it into the labor market and adjust career guidance accordingly;

Benchmarking career guidance marketing communications and services against international best practice is necessary.

In order to inform students and their parents about the realities of the labor market, the government needs to implement Graduate Destination Surveys for bachelors and master's degrees, graduate salaries, graduate course experience, and postgraduate research experience.

In order for students and their parents to compare information about employment outcomes and student satisfaction across higher education providers, the government needs to launch a website containing data from the Graduate Destination Surveys.

- The government must use social media to communicate with students and parents and invite them to collaborate on the creation of well-informed media communications;
- The government must ensure that universities evaluate and continually improve the relevance of graduate attributes based on the priorities of the labor market;

It is the democratic duty of the government to provide students and their parents with relevant, pertinent information so that they can make educated career and educational choices that are in line with the capacity of the labor market to absorb talent.

Relevance to Kanchanaburi Rajabhat University's context the findings of the research have particular significance for Kanchanaburi Rajabhat University, which served as the setting for the field research. The following are suggestions. Specifically:

Prior to enrollment, prospective students and their parents must be made aware of the connection between student course selection and labor market absorptive capacity and priorities.

Prior to enrollment, prospective students must be made aware of the connection that exists between course selection and strategic AEC opportunities;

The University must improve its career guidance, particularly with regard to: (1) a website and social media apps for students and parents to compare employment outcomes and student satisfaction with other higher education providers, as well as aptitude and career matching;

To guarantee the relevance of course outcomes, the university must adopt and measure quality standards.

- The University must continually assess and improve the relevance of graduate attributes that are in line with the priorities of the labor market;
- The University must monitor and evaluate the role of seniors (graduates and senior students) in enrollment procedures;
- The University must improve academics' and students' ability to think critically and creatively in the following areas:
 - the growth of patents and copyrights owned by universities;
 - the creation of novel student-run start-up employment opportunities;
- The University must conduct annual Graduate Destination Surveys as an evaluation tool for all of the aforementioned;

- The university must update its curricula and teaching methods in order to maintain its Thai identity in a labor market that is becoming increasingly globalized.

It is acknowledged that the faculties of the university are currently participating in some or all of the aforementioned activities to varying degrees.

Government Policies and Industry Expectations The findings of this research paper demonstrate instances of policy abandonment by various Thai governments. There have been eleven National Economic and Social Development Plans issued over the past half century, but no reports on how each plan's goals and objectives have progressed have been published. Education reforms reappear in subsequent plans, but little progress is actually made, possibly due to the lack of published key performance indicators for measuring goals and objectives. Mephokee (2003) had previously noted that government institutions' reliance on policy repetition was a weakness in this regard.

A relevant example is Prime Minister Abhisit Vejjajiva's 2010 Creative Thailand Policy, which was mentioned in Section 1.4 (iii) above and was announced, promoted, and then abandoned within twenty-four months. Therefore, students enrolled in courses that fulfill an abandoned government priority can be held accountable by universities that are expected to respond with relevant curricula. However, the goals of the Creative Thailand Policy of 2010 to boost Thailand's GDP by 8% through the creative industries were based on a number of well-researched studies and strategies that, if implemented, could have absorbed a large number of university graduates into the Thai labor market (Kenan Institute Asia, 2009). However, Thai industry did not find the 2010 Creative Thailand Policy to be in line with the predominant manufacturing orientation based on foreign direct investment. Mephokee (2003) had previously attributed the resistance to the development of new labor skills to the structure of Thai industry, specifically the low private sector investment in R&D.

As a result, faculty members interviewed for this study suggest that university faculties might be responsive to government priorities for the labor market. However, this research paper acknowledges that government priorities change and even disappear without considering the long-term impact of the already underway reorientation of university curricula, leaving universities struggling to catch up. This makes attributes of a university graduate difficult to understand and elaborate on within specific contexts (see Chapman, 2004), particularly when the contexts are generalized across multiple industry sectors, which Thai employers appear to anticipate. To put it succinctly, the future prosperity of Thai industry and the labor market will require greater long-term planning and collaboration on the part of the government, industry, and universities.

AN ENTREPRENEURIAL APPROACH

One implicit assumption of the relationship between university study choice and the labor market is that the labor market alone determines the nature of work and, as a result, the jobs that contribute to the economy (or at least the vast majority of jobs). However, research from Florida (2002, 2010, 2014) and others (Henry and de Bruin 2011, Zhao 2012, Moretti 2013) suggests that

Western nations have developed a creative class that is largely responsible for job creation and national wealth⁴³. According to Zhao (2012), graduates need to be resourceful, adaptable, and creative in order to succeed in the global economy. Universities also need to help students develop their entrepreneurial skills, encourage student autonomy and leadership, champion invention, and establish global partnerships. The Thai education system, on the other hand, is depicted in this research paper's literature review as fixated on rote learning and the pursuit of high graduation scores, which advance institutional prestige rather than entrepreneurship.

A study on Thailand's internationalization of higher education (Chalapati, 2007) raises these concerns and concludes that Thailand's response to international trends is inconsistent in terms of what higher education is or should be focused on. Among the issues identified are: the academic staff's failure to demonstrate the subjects' utility; a common misconception that low classroom interaction levels or a lack of them are typical aspects of Thai culture and should not be considered a problem; the lack of awareness of opportunities for networking with international students enrolled in Thai universities; and the skepticism of foreign students regarding the high grades that were given (Chalapati, 2007).

Therefore, it is not just the quantity of education provided but also its relevance and quality to provide skills that enhance learning abilities, adopt new technologies, and create new environments that support economic growth. Therefore, it is argued that the goal of Thai universities and the education system should not just be to meet employers' demands for work, but also to foster creative thinking about and application of knowledge so that Thailand develops a creative class that can create its own employment opportunities. Although science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) education is advanced in Thailand and is one of the highest-paying, fastest-growing, and most influential categories driving economic growth (Jimenez et al. 2012), creative innovation will be necessary to advance Thailand to the status of a first-world economy. This aspect is something that the equation of education to the existing Thai labor market tends to ignore, but it may provide Thailand with greater potential for a prosperous economic future than relying solely on manufacturing.

CONCLUSION

The following four fundamental research questions are addressed by this study's findings:

(i) How connected are student degree choices and priorities in the Thai labor market currently?

At this time, there is essentially no connection between student degree choice and priorities in the Thai labor market. There are few marketing communications for career guidance that inform students and their parents.

(ii) In Thailand, who influences individual undergraduate degree selection and subsequent career choice?

Parents, high school teachers, and career brochures ad hoc influence Thai students' decisions regarding undergraduate study and subsequent career choice;

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(iii) How can marketing communications increase awareness of career guidance for Thai job seekers?

In Thailand, marketing communications play a minimal or nonexistent role in raising awareness of career guidance for career choice. It lacks the essential features described in the previous paper. As a result, Thailand's labor market priorities and undergraduate study choice are hindered by inadequate marketing communications.

(iv) What factors contribute to the gap between Thailand's priorities for the labor market and graduate unemployment?

In Thailand, the gap between graduate unemployment and priorities in the labor market is caused by the following factors: a lack of data on the supply and demand of jobs in the labor market; a dearth of user-friendly online portals and bulletin boards for disseminating pertinent information; an uncoordinated approach to career guidance by government agencies, businesses, and educational institutions; a lack of awareness on the part of students and their parents of the significance of career guidance; a lack of a brand identity that identifies the requirements that career counseling serves for students, parents, and the national economy; a lack of a service-oriented logic that would encourage educators, students, parents, and employers to interact with the government and continuously improve career guidance services; a lack of ownership over career guidance and accountability within a single authority; the preponderance of bureaucratic-centricity over student-centricity in determining student career choice in relation to priorities in the labor market; a dearth of measurement and evaluation of the provision of career guidance services; a lack of synergy to provide a quality-standards-based suite of interconnected services; a lack of benchmarks for career guidance; and the government's lack of graduate destination surveys and student feedback.

According to Bussi (cited by Le Fevre 2013b), there is a lack of capacity to promote, advertise, and identify the kinds of skills required by the Thai labor market. This conclusion is supported by the research. According to the findings of this research paper, there is a lack of effective marketing communications to educate students, parents, and universities about career guidance in Thailand. Therefore, the prevalent assumptions and practices of career guidance in Thailand do not correspond to the assumed requirements for higher education to produce an informed and relevant labor market.

According to the findings of the research paper, career guidance in Thailand does not contribute to the expansion of the Thai labor market by facilitating the transfer of higher education knowledge and skills. It appears that Thai industry is unwilling to move toward an economy based on knowledge, and higher education appears to be hesitant to implement relevant critical and creative pedagogy. As a result, higher education's transformation from a means to an end to a means of national economic growth is stifled. Based on the findings of this research paper, it is possible to draw the conclusion that career guidance in Thailand is incompatible with the prevalent ethos of a labor market that is becoming increasingly globalized.

This study's qualitative methodology combined career guidance, undergraduate study choice, and Thailand's labor market priorities in a trans disciplinary configuration, yielding 28 preliminary findings primarily, but not exclusively, related to the failure of career guidance marketing communication. It is argued that the research paper's applied data and theoretical knowledge significantly expand our understanding of Thailand's socioeconomic development. A comprehensive analysis of Thai career guidance in light of the economic realities of the labor market is possible thanks to the evaluative framework.

As a result, it is concluded that the findings of this research paper contribute to the theory and practice of career guidance and the Thai labor market, as well as to the body of knowledge regarding associated professional practices.

Additionally, I now know that writing a research paper takes time and requires overcoming numerous contradictions; that data must be developed logically; that research can go in many different directions when it crosses disciplines; and, perhaps most importantly, that Thai university graduates require assistance choosing their undergraduate degree and becoming productive contributors to the nation's economic advantage. Marketing communications has a lot to offer in this direction.

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